

Antecedents Of Behavioral Intention Factors In Influencing User Acceptance Of E-Learning At Applied Science Privet University

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 30, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: September 30, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords User acceptance of E-learning, Microsoft team, technology acceptance model</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4061198</p>	<p><i>This study investigates the status of the Microsoft team application as a part of E-learning amongst business administration students at Applied Science Privet University. The objective of this study is to analyze the impact of the perceived usefulness, the perceived ease of use and E-training on the behavioral intentions of students. It also explored the effects of the above-mentioned factors on user acceptance of E-learning. The mediating factor of this study is behavioral intention on user acceptance of E-learning. The researcher used questionnaires to fulfill the objectives of the study. The researcher distributed the questionnaires through email. The sampling of this research was 100 students from college of business administration. The researcher used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique to analyze the results. The most important limitation in this study is that the results cannot be universal since the study was limited to business administration faculty at Applied Science Privet University.</i></p>

1. Introduction

The personal computer and the Internet have played a prominent role in changing working life; this technology has changed the way individuals work, communicate, market and learn. E-learning is a form of traditional education linked to the convergence of courses (Allen & Seaman, 2004). Currently, communication tools such as email and teleconferencing have been available to all students worldwide (Theriot, 2004; Masa'deh et al., 2013).

One of the applications called Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is used to explain how users adopt a new technology. This study examines an extension of the TAM by demonstrating how the social impact and application characteristics influence the behavioral intention of college students for applications such as the Microsoft team. As people spend more time using an application, organizations think of the application as a new primary way to enhance customer experience and build customer relationships, leading to increased customer engagement and loyalty (Racherla, Furner, & Babb, 2012). The Microsoft team is a key part of E-learning. To promote the Microsoft team, the TAM (Davis, 1989; Davis, Bagozzi, & Warshaw, 1989) has been widely applied to demonstrate how users adopt a new technology. The three determinants that affect user decisions include perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and E-training. The TAM has become a solid model for predicting user acceptance of technology over the past decade.

E-learning study remains the main issue in many different sectors and environments (Nahid et al., 2019).

A few studies have been found to integrate the effect of social impact, such as ease of use, usefulness, E-training and system features with the TAM to demonstrate the behavioral intent for users of the Microsoft team. To fill this gap, this study attempts to determine the factors that affect students' acceptance of the Microsoft team by determining whether the three factors listed above affect behavioral intention. Specifically, the analysis focuses on how students perceive the usefulness of and the ease with which the Microsoft team can be perceived.

2-Motivation of the study

The importance of this study is that it tries to identify the factors that encourage the use of the E-learning system established by most universities in Jordan and that the cost required by preparing this system to provide the necessary financial resources and qualified human resources is worthy of conducting such a study. However, the factors that affect its acceptance still need to be investigated further (Alshammari, Ali, & Rosli, 2016). The importance of this study is also that it provides feedback to decision-makers in universities as it seeks to uncover obstacles, problems and justifications that limit the use of this system by students by strengthening existing strengths, diagnosing and working to eliminate weaknesses and raise the required level for the educational process. Using E-learning to improve education is a technology available in most parts of the world (Tarhini et al., 2014). In this study, the focus will be on most of the factors that contribute to the technological acceptance by university students; this depends on the amount of information that can be provided and that can contribute to technological acceptance in a way that enhances the students' acceptance of the idea of E-learning. This study

also aims to examine the theoretical concept of user acceptance of E-learning and its comparison with practices in universities. By understanding the application of the Microsoft team user acceptance of E-learning, some practical recommendations can be made to reduce the gap of user acceptance of E-learning for the Microsoft team. Consequently, this research funds to define and assess the success factors which can reduce the user acceptance of the E-learning gap.

3-Research model and hypotheses development

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) and the TAM established by Davis (1989), Taylor and Todd (1995), Venkatesh and Davis (1996) guide the research model which is adopted in this study (Davis, F.D., 1989). Taylor and Todd (1995) provided experimental support to demonstrate that IT acceptance could be explained by the UTAUT model (Taylor, S. & Todd, P., 1995). This paper examines the direct impact of perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and E-training on behavioral intention and the effect of behavioral intention on user acceptance of E-learning. In addition, this paper examines the intermediate impact of behavioral intention between perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and E-training on user acceptance of E-learning. Moreover, the direct effect of the above three factors on user acceptance of E-learning. (See Figure 1).

Figure1:The Research model

Perceived Usefulness (PU): Perceived benefit or PU indicates the degree to which individuals expect that the use of new technology can improve their job performance (Chinyamurindi & Shava, 2015). Various empirical studies have indicated that PU is the primary determinant for the use of a particular technique (Chow, Herold, Choo, & Chan, 2012). The E-learning system can be considered an information technology tool, and the system will only be accepted by students when they see that using it will improve their educational performance. Hence, in relation to E-learning, PU indicates the degree to which students see that the use of the E-learning system will enhance the learning performance.

Therefore, we posited the following:

H1: The perceived usefulness will have a positive influence on the behavioral intention.

Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU): PEOU refers to the system as how an individual realizes that using a particular technology will not be complicated (Cheng, Y., 2011). It has been proven in many studies that PEOU has a positive relationship with the behavioral intention (BI) to use technology directly and indirectly (Cheng, Y. M., 2012). With regard to e-learning, PEOU indicates to what extent the student believes that using the e-learning system will require a little effort and will be easy to use. The interaction between students and E-learning is clear and understandable (B. Cheng, Wang, Moormann, Olaniran, & Chen, 2012).

The hypotheses are formalized as below:

H2: The perceived ease of use has a positive influence on the behavioral intention

E-Training

Training increases the ability of individuals to use information systems applications (Compeau, Higgins & Huff, 1999), as training programs are usually given prior to implementing information systems applications because of the importance of this. The integration of information systems applications motivates users to learn new skills, so most studies have concluded that the persistent lack of learning about new technological skills will cause a gap between the actual use of information technology and the trend of individuals towards the use of information technology (Doll et al., 2003). Therefore, the following is hypothesized:

H3: E-training has a positive influence on the behavioral intention. Behavioral Intention (BI): (Fathema, Shannon, & Ross, 2015) stated that BI talks about the intention of learners to use the e-learning system and contains tenacious use throughout the ages. Various studies such as (Ghosh, 2016) show that BI uses the system directly and greatly influences the use of the actual system (AU) for e-learning. Therefore, the researcher verifies the following hypothesis :

H4: Behavioral intention has a positive effect on the user acceptance of E-learning. The mediation effect on behavioral intent: In this study, researchers assumed BI as a mediator in the relationship between factors (PU, PEOU, e-training) and user acceptance of e-learning.

Therefore, we test the following hypotheses:

H5: Behavioral intention will have mediating effect between perceived usefulness and user acceptance of E-learning.

H6: Behavioral intention will have mediating effect between ease of use and user acceptance of E-learning.

H7: Behavioral intention will have mediating effect between E-training and user acceptance of E-learning.

Direct Effect of Factors on User Acceptance of E-learning: In this study, the researchers hypothesized a direct relationship between the factors in the framework (PU, PEOU, E-training) and user acceptance of E-learning in order to show which of these factors has significant effect on user acceptance of E-learning.

H8: Perceived usefulness will influence user acceptance of E-learning.

H9: Perceived ease of use will influence user acceptance of E-learning.

H10: E-training will influence user acceptance of E-learning.

4-Research methodology

Research measures, sample and data collection

Researchers have developed a field survey of business school students. All research structures were measured using seven-point Likert scale elements with closed ends, with scales ranging from 1¼ “Strongly Disagree” to 4¼ “Strongly Disagree” to 7 “Strongly Agree”. The elements used to measure the constructs of behavioral intent were modified from Taylor and Todd (1995), while the elements measuring perceived ease of use and the concept of perceived usefulness were modified from Davis (1989). In addition, items that measure user acceptance of E-learning were modified by Wang, et al (2003). The elements that measure electronic training (Tarawneh, M. & Tarawneh, H., 2011) have also been modified.

Five Jordanian students and three academic professors in Management Information Systems participated in a pilot test. Then they commented on the contents of the questionnaire and its general appearance, and adjustments were made to the survey. The researcher chose Applied Science Private University to carry out the data collection. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2013), non-probability sampling designs consist of easy sampling and purposeful sampling (i.e., sampling and quotas); this study uses non-probability sampling and enables researchers to choose a number of students who use the Microsoft team.

The researcher chooses this college based on teaching subjects such as knowledge management for all students of business administration and data mining, decision support systems in addition to analysis and design of the advanced system and the high level of development in the application of the Microsoft team in general, which is accepted for the objectives of the study. The sampling method used was judgment sampling, which is a type of purposive sampling in which the researchers' selected specific faculty as a unit of analysis according to some previously defined criteria. Data for this research was obtained from students of Applied Science Privet University. The target population of this process, which contributes to the success of Microsoft teams, is students in selected faculty's business administration courses that have implemented Microsoft teams. The total number of faculty stood at one faculty. A total of 80 returned the survey.

Table 1 shows consists of gender and field of education.

Table 1. Characteristics of the respondents. (N = 80)

Characteristics	Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	42	52%
Female	38	48%
Field of education		
MIS	42	53%
Business administration	29	36%

Finance	3	4%
Accounting	4	5%
Marketing	2	2%

Data analysis and results

Structure Reliability Assessment in order to continue SEM analysis, it is necessary to evaluate each link's reliability measure using Alpha Cronbach. Some researchers (Hair et al., 2006) recommend Alpha-Cronbach values between 0.60 and 0.70 (Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W., 1976). Whereas the description of scale elements as well as the reliability of the observed elements in survey structures are displayed in a range of 0.71 - 0.86, as shown in Table 2, all research structures exceeded the recommended value for Alpha Cronbach (i.e., between 0.60 and 0.70), thus revealing the degree of. Satisfactory reliability and compound reliability values ranged from 0.71 to 0.81 as shown in the Table 3, all of which were in the recommended range of greater than 0.60 (Bagozzi, R. & Yi, Y., 1988).

Assessing the validity of the constructs

While the convergence validity test is important in the measurement model to check if indicators in the volume scale come together in one structure, the discriminatory validity test is also important to confirm whether the elements developed to measure different structures are evaluating completely different structures.

Table 2. Reliabilities of the scales. (N = 80)

Constructs	Indicators	Cronbach's Alpha
Perceived usefulness	PU1- PU4	0.74
Perceived ease of use	PE1- PE4	0.80
E-training	ET1- ET4	0.86
Behavioral intention	BI1-BI4	0.79
User acceptance of E-learning	UA1-UA4	0.71

Convergent validity

Some researchers have argued (for example, Schwab, D. 1980) that affinity is ascertained when standard regression weights are important (Schwab, D., 1980). Also, Bollen, (1989) emphasized that the higher the load factor, the stronger the indication that the measured measures represent the groups.

As shown in Table 2, the researchers examined the standard regression weights of the research indices and found that some indices had a low load toward the underlying variables (i.e., less than 0.50, which is the standard value recommended by Newkirk and Lederer (2006)). In particular, (PU4 = 0.126, PE2 = 0.412, ET4 = 0.351, BI1 = 0.261, UA4 = 0.329). Since all of these elements did not meet the recommended minimum value for a 0.50 download factor (Newkirk and Lederer, 2006), they were removed and excluded from further analysis.

Discriminant validity

Discrimination was validated using several tests. Fronel and Larker (1981) argued that the validity differentiation in the measurement model could be examined by investigating the AVE by means of latent groups. Also, the connections between research structures can be used to measure the validity of the distinction by examining whether there are any very large associations between them.

Table 3. Reliability and factor loadings.

Construct	Factor loading	Composite reliability
Perceived usefulness		0.78
PU1	0.664	
PU2	0.532	
PU3	0.617	
Perceived ease of use		0.71
PE1	0.541	
PE3	0.731	
PE4	0.594	
E-training		0.73
ET1	0.826	
ET2	0.544	
ET3	0.562	
Behavioral intention		0.77
BI2	0.781	
BI3	0.634	

BI4	0.621	
User acceptance of E-learning		0.81
UA1	0.893	
UA2	0.712	
UA3	0.655	

Presence of Such Very Large Correlations. In addition, if the AVE for each structure exceeds the square correlation between this structure and any other structure, discriminatory validity occurs (Fronell & Larcker, 1981). As shown in Table 4 and the use of the Fronell and Larker formula (1981) to calculate the average variance extracted from a latent structure, this study showed that all combinations showed 50 percent or more of the variance, ranging from 0.65 to 0.81, which fulfilled the recommendation that AVE values should be at least 0.50 per build (Blunch, N.J., Title, B., Equation, S., Using, M., Title, A.C., Date, A., et al., 2008). Further, as shown in Table 4, the distinction was validated where the AVE values were more than the square associations for each set of structures. Therefore, it measures very differentiated structures.

Assessment of measurement model

In order to have a statistical effect on the model fit for a dataset, the maximum probability estimate (ML) is appropriate in SEM for several reasons. First, the ML method is a widely used estimation method, especially with limited sample sizes from 100 to 200 (Anderson, J. & Gerbing, D., 1988). Also, it is applied to estimate all model parameters simultaneously (Kline, R.B., 2011). The χ^2/df ratio is also an indicator that requires three values or fewer for an acceptable model (Kline, R.B., 2011). In this case, the smaller the percentage value, the better. However, some researchers (for example, James et al., 1982) recommended that the ratio be between 2 and 5 (James, L., Mulaik, S., & Brett, J., 1982). Moreover, if the values of AGFI, NFI, IFI, TLI, and CFI range from 0.80 to 0.90, then they are considered acceptable (Bentler, P.M. & Bonett, D.G., 1980). The RMSEA value takes the goodness-of-fit of the model into account. The accepted values should range from 0.05 to 0.08 (Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W., 1976). Accordingly, the result confirmed that the measurement model fits with the data collected (see Table 5).

Table 4: AVE and square of correlations between constructs.

	PU	PE	ET	BI	UA
PU	0.66				
PE	0.162	0.74			
ET	0.151	0.151	0.67		
BI	0.142	0.126	0.157	0.81	
UA	0.127	0.138	0.129	0.128	0.65

(Note: Diagonal elements are the average variance extracted for each of the five constructs. Off-diagonal elements are the squared correlations between constructs.)

Table 5. Fit indices for measurement and structural model.

Quality of fit measure	Recommended value	Measurement model	Structural model
χ^2/df	2 to 5	1.21	2.78
AGFI	0.80 to 0.90	0.51	0.94
CFI	0.80 to 0.90	0.62	0.94
TLI	0.80 to 0.90	0.67	0.88
IFI	0.80 to 0.90	0.72	0.81
NFI	0.80 to 0.90	0.75	0.86
RMSEA	0.05 to 0.08	0.018	0.061

5-Hypotheses testing and results of the study

The findings from the empirical study, as shown in this study, presented interesting results for discussion, which extended previously research in the areas of behavioral intention and user acceptance of E-learning. As noted in Table 6, seven propositions related to the aims of this study were developed and tested. Out of the seven proposed relationships, six were supported and one was not. Table 7 presents each parameter's C.R. estimate. Based on the results provided, it is clear that perceived usefulness has insignificant impact on behavioral intention ($P = 0.313$). Therefore, H1 is not supported. H2 is supported, as perceived ease of use has a significant positive on behavioral intention ($P = ***$). H3 is supported because E-training has a significant impact on behavioral intention ($P = 0.036$). For H4, behavioral intention has a positive significant impact on user acceptance of E-learning ($P = 0.024$), indicating support for it. Perceived usefulness has a positive significant impact on user acceptance of E-learning ($P = 0.074$), indicating that H5 is also supported. In addition, for H6, the perceived ease of use is found to have a positive direct impact on user acceptance of E-learning ($P = 0.062$), also indicating the support for it. In addition, E-training is found to have an impact on user acceptance of E-learning ($P = 0.002$), indicating that H7 was accepted.

Table 6: Summary of proposed results for the theoretical model.

Research proposed paths	t-value (CR)	Coefficient value (std. estim)	P-value	Results
PU $\Rightarrow$ BI	3.21	1.11	0.313	Not Supported
PE $\Rightarrow$ BI	5.013	3.201	***	Supported
ET $\Rightarrow$ BI	3.604	1.602	0.036	Supported
BI $\Rightarrow$ UA	5.25	4.01	0.024	Supported
PU $\Rightarrow$ UA	4.103	5.104	0.074	Supported
PE $\Rightarrow$ UA	3.71	4.11	0.062	Supported
ET $\Rightarrow$ UA	4.55	3.06	0.002	Supported

(***P $\leq$ 0.005, **P $\leq$ 0.01, *P $\leq$ 0.05). Notes: Path = Relationship between independent variable on dependent variable; C.R. = Critical ration; S.E. = Standard error; P = Level of significance.

Results of behavioral intention as a mediating effect

For this study, the researchers tested the mediating effects of behavioral intention on the relationship between the perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and E-training and user acceptance of E-learning as shown in Table 7. The insignificant result of the empirical finding (the direct effect of 0.005 is more than the indirect effect of 0.002) confirmed that behavioral intention did not mediate the relationship between E-training and user acceptance of E-learning. This finding did not support H7. In contrast, the significant empirical result (the direct effect of 0.123 is less than the indirect effect of 0.022) confirmed that behavioral intention mediated the relationship between perceived usefulness and user acceptance of E-learning. Consequently, H5 was supported. Another significant result of the empirical finding (the direct effect of 0.034 is less than the indirect effect of 0.061) confirmed that behavioral intention mediated the relationship between perceived ease of use and user acceptance of E-learning. Hence, H6 was supported.

Table 7. Summary of proposed results for the theoretical model.

Hypothesis	From	Mediation	To	Direct effect	Indirect effect	Total effect	Results
H5	PU	BI	UA	0.123	0.022	0.145	Supported
H6	PE	BI	UA	0.034	0.061	0.095	Supported
H7	ET	BI	UA	0.005	0.002	0.007	Not Supported

6-Discussion, conclusions and further research

Through a review of the literature related to E-learning, a focus was placed on a set of factors that are considered to be components of the technology acceptance model, in addition to the need to demonstrate the importance of training students to interact effectively with E-learning systems. E-learning literature was verified, and the most important factors that could affect students' acceptance of the E-learning environment in Jordanian universities were verified. A model consisting of a set of factors such as ease of use, usefulness and E-training was developed. The findings have shown that user acceptance of E-learning can be verified by perceived ease of use and E-training. The findings further highlighted the fitness of using the revised UTAUT model and TAM in accepting user behavioral intention and user acceptance of E-learning in relation to E-learning. From the point of view of this study, perceived ease of use and E-training have significant impact of behavioral intention. These findings are consistent with most prior research in technology acceptance (Wang, Y.S. & Shih, Y.W., 2008). In addition, perceived ease of use is significant of behavioral intention. Furthermore, behavioral intention has a significant impact on user acceptance of E-learning. Also, this study found significant effects of perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and E-Training on user acceptance of E-learning. This study found that there were mediating effects between behavioral intention, perceived usefulness and user acceptance of E-learning, while there was no mediating effect with behavioral intention on the relationship between E-training and user acceptance of E-learning. This result confirmed that there was an insignificant impact of E-training on behavioral intention of user acceptance of E-learning. This study found that there were mediating effects between behavioral intention, perceived ease of use and user acceptance of E-learning.

Empirical research was performed with the intention of investigating the determinants of user acceptance of E-learning in Jordan. The present study does not include educational environment as a factor. Future research should study the effect of this variable on the determinants of user acceptance of E-learning. The study could also be extended to other universities operating in comparable conditions to see if similar results could be recognized. Finally, the data and results reported in this study were based on a single country, Jordan. Thus, they are applicable specifically in the Jordanian context. This raises questions regarding the generalization of the findings for other contexts. As a result, further research is needed in other countries to help advance the understanding of the user acceptance of E-learning issue in other countries.

7-References

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